

Telia Rumal : A Traditional and Sustainable Textile of Telangana

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The hand-woven textiles of India not only represent the rich heritage of Indian tradition but also provide a large source of employment. After agriculture, handloom sector is one of the largest economic activities of India which provides employment to almost 35.23 lakh weavers directly and indirectly. In the era of new technologies and changing market preferences there is vital need of preservation of these traditional knowledge. Telia rumal is one of the few sustainable textiles of India, which lost its popularity a few decades ago and now a days practiced by only one village of Telangana. GI tag has been awarded to Telia Rumal in 2020 for being a unique variety of double Ikat natural dyed hand woven textile. It is also known as fisherman's cloth, because of its popularity among the fishermen. The textile has three unique features. First of all, its unique dyeing technique, using of *tel* or oil. Second, the textile is weather- friendly, in the hot summer it provides comfort and in the cold winter it feels warm. The last feature is the intricate square grid designs with three colours.

The aim of this research paper is to show the development of Telia rumal textile analysing its characteristics. This study highlights the need of handloom textiles in the society as well as the sustainable aspect of it. It also discusses the role of Crafts Council of Telangana in reviving and bringing out the new possibilities of Telia Rumal.

Keywords: Indian Textile, Traditional Knowledge, Ikat, Telia Rumal, Sustainability.